
Research

Designing a Strategic Framework for Advancing Capabilities in Adopting AI/ML Technologies for Supply Chain Management

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Abstract: This research aims to propose a unique framework that is meant to boost the capacities of supply chain organizations to effectively embrace and make use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) technologies. The framework will be presented in order to accomplish this purpose. For the goal of better preparing students to cope with the unanticipated and ever-changing aspects of supply chain operations, the objective of this course is to enhance students' knowledge and skills in the areas of data administration, analytical competence, and performance management. Data management capabilities that focus on data governance and quality; analytical competence for identifying appropriate AI/ML applications in various supply chain aspects; and performance management skills that make use of the Six Sigma DMAIC method and KPI dashboards are the three primary components that make up the framework that has been proposed. These are the three primary components that make up the framework. doing interviews with subject matter experts, building a framework, and doing in-depth research on the existing body of literature are all steps that are included in the process of evaluating the subject matter. As a result of the findings, it is possible to draw the conclusion that this framework offers a major contribution to the improvement of decision-making, operational efficiency, and competitiveness in the field of supply chain management. Volatility, uncertainty, complexity, and ambiguity are the components that make up the acronym VUCA. This acronym incorporates the issues that are presented by the environment in which businesses operate. Despite these limitations, it is able to successfully adjust. The objective of this research is to provide assistance to supply chain firms in the process of successfully implementing technologies that utilize artificial intelligence and machine learning. In addition to this, it suggests a methodical approach to the development of vital competences in order to get ready for future technological breakthroughs.

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Introduction

Within the dynamic realm of supply chain management, firms consistently face the challenges posed by environmental risks and the constantly shifting wants of consumers. The combination of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) technologies has become a crucial answer to these difficulties, providing unparalleled possibilities for streamlining and creativity. Nevertheless, achieving successful integration and optimal exploitation of these technologies necessitates a sophisticated comprehension and cultivation of distinct organizational competencies. In recent years, there have been notable changes in the way supply chain operations are conducted. Volatility, uncertainty, complexity, and ambiguity—sometimes referred to as VUCA—are characteristics of these changes. The volatile nature of this environment requires a more adaptable and proactive approach to managing the supply chain. Although AI and ML technologies hold the potential to tackle these difficulties, their incorporation into supply chain processes is not a simple process. A strategic framework is required to properly utilize these technologies in enterprises. This article aims to fill this significant void by presenting a complete framework that is specifically designed to foster crucial competencies within supply chain businesses, enabling them to effectively embrace and utilize AI/ML technology. The research is motivated by the acknowledgement that the ever-changing nature of customer demand and the intricacies of contemporary supply chains necessitate a methodical approach to data management, analytical proficiency, and performance management. The main goal of this study is to create and assess a framework that allows businesses to construct and enhance these talents. The study intends to provide a path for supply chain companies as they navigate the complexity of integrating technology. It focuses on data governance, quality, and the strategic utilization of AI/ML technologies to enhance decision-making and operational efficiency. The purpose of this introduction is to provide a comprehensive examination of the proposed framework, including its various components and the methodology used to build and evaluate it. This research adds to the current knowledge by providing a realistic and organized method for improving supply chain capabilities in the context of adopting AI/ML technology. It addresses a crucial requirement in the field of supply chain management.

Fig. 1: DSMR Process Model (Peffer et al., 2017)

Literature review

Research Procedure: The systematic literature review (SLR) method, as put forth by Kitchenham and Charters (Group, 2007), is the chosen research strategy for this study. In accordance with the prescribed criteria, our systematic literature review (SLR) was executed in a sequential manner, comprising three distinct phases: planning, execution, and documentation. The initial phase of the planning process involves the formulation of research inquiries and the development of a review protocol. The subsequent phase entails conducting research, which involves determining the criteria for inclusion and exclusion, selecting appropriate databases, and executing the search. The documentation stage, which is the third phase, involves the process of selecting relevant research. During this stage, a comprehensive list of included and excluded studies is compiled, and the quality of primary studies is evaluated (Figure 2).

Fig.2: Process of the SLR Method

Literature Review Research: Artificial intelligence and machine learning in supply chain operations are the focus of the research. These inquiries examine supply chain management difficulties, measurements, and requirements.

- RQ1. What does the literature say about supply chain AI/ML use?
- RQ2. The literature examines how artificial intelligence and machine learning technology have alleviated supply chain challenges.
- RQ3. Artificial intelligence and machine learning in supply chain operations are evaluated using which KPIs?
- RQ4. The research implies that AI/ML technology application in supply chain operations requires certain competencies?

RQ1 analyses the use of AI and ML in supply chain operations and Sales and Operations Planning. RQ2 investigates how AI and ML technologies have solved supply chain operations and sales and operations planning (S&OP) problems. According to the literature, RQ3 is investigated because AI/ML technologies can produce quantifiable results in supply chain operations and sales and operations planning. AI and machine learning performance in organizational operations will be measured using these criteria. RQ4 was created to discover and understand the skills needed to integrate cutting-edge technologies into supply chain management.

Experimental setup

Table 1 shows the number of papers retrieved from various sources in the chosen databases using the search instructions in next Section. The initial search yielded 380 papers from five databases. 90 papers were selected from this pool using the criteria in the previous sections. After rigorous analysis, 35 duplicate works were found. This study reviewed 54 papers to find reliable information.

Sources	RQ1	RQ2	RQ3	RQ4	Total
Scopus	9	1	2	2	14
Taylor and Francis	4	3	1	1	9
ScienceDirect – Elsevier	10	6	1	5	22
Emerald	3	-	4	1	8
MPDI	-	1	-	-	1
Total selected papers	26	11	8	9	54

Table 1: Articles Discovered and Chosen Based on RQs

The next sections offer a summary of the selected articles and their findings, aiming to address each study question.

- The existing body of literature explores the uses of artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) technologies in the domain of supply chain operations.**

Data was divided into five supply chain domains to answer RQ1. Table 2 shows the implementation of artificial intelligence and machine learning in the five key domains' subdomains.

Field	Sub-fields	Sources
Sales planning	Sales forecasting	(Chang et al., 2008), (W. I. Lee et al., 2012)
	Sales promotion	(O'Donnell et al., 2009)
	Sales promotion	(Shakya et al., 2010)
	Marketing decision support	(Stalidis et al., 2015)
	New products specification design	(Kwong et al., 2016)
	Product life-cycle management	(Taratukhin & Yadgarova, 2018)
Logistics	Inbound logistics processes	(Knoll et al., 2016)
	Logistics systems automation	(Klumpp, 2018)
	Logistics workflow	(Ho et al., 2006), (C. K. M. Lee et al., 2011)
Production	Production mentoring	(Guo et al., 2015)
	Production forecasting	(Elsheikh et al., 2021), (NEGASH & YAW, 2020)
	Production planning and scheduling	(Ławrynowicz, 2008)
	Quality control and improvement monitoring	(Taylan & Darrab, 2012)
	Product line optimization	(Waschneck et al., 2018)
Supply Chain	Demand forecasting	(Amirkolaii et al., 2017), (Mobarakeh et al., 2017), (Efendigil et al., 2009)
	Supplier selection	(Ferreira & Borenstein, 2012), (Vahdani et al., 2012)
	Supply chain network design	(Zhang et al., 2017)
	Supply chain risk management	(Baryannis et al., 2019)
	Inventory replenishment	(Sinha et al., 2012)
S&OP	Integrated Business Planning	(Schlegel et al., 2020)

Table 2 The findings pertaining to RQ 1

Artificial intelligence and machine learning in supply chain operations give supply chains intelligence, according to the report. These capabilities could boost operational and supply chain efficiency. Automation of repeated manual operations illustrates this. AI and ML are used in supply planning, production, logistics, and operational planning.

- The topic of discussion pertains to the concept of sales planning:

Seven articles cover sales planning. Three scholarly publications handle distinct sales topics. The first two articles cover sales forecasting, while the third covers sales promotion. Chang et al. (2008) and W. I. Lee et al. (2012) independently suggested hybrid artificial intelligence models to improve sales projections across organizations. Chang et al. (2008) created the fuzzy case-based reasoning (FCBR) model to improve sales estimates by incorporating fuzzy theory into case-based reasoning. Lee et al. (2012) developed ECFM (Enhanced Cluster and Forecast Model) sales forecasting using self-organizing maps (SOM) and radial basis function (RBF) neural networks. The approach improves revenue forecast accuracy, improving firm planning efficiency and revenue. O'Donnell et al. (2009) found that using the genetic algorithm (GA) can reduce the bullwhip effect and save money in an online investigation. The GA also helped supply managers predict supply chain reorder volumes and organize promotional actions. Shakya et al. (2010) propose a pricing system using five AI methods. This method may produce pricing strategies for a variety of goods and services regardless of the demand model. The Stalidis et al. (2015) marketing decision help framework uses Artificial Neural Network (ANN) technology. In their study, Kwong et al. (2016) combined design, engineering, and marketing approaches to specify unique product designs. It integrates using genetic algorithms (GA) with fuzzy models. The suggested methodology focuses on creating and refining customer satisfaction and cost models. Taratukhin and Yadgarova (2018) suggested using a multi-agent system (MAS) to manage product life cycles.

- The field of logistics encompasses the management and coordination of various activities involved in the movement and storage:

Logistics includes four items. Using machine learning (ML), Knoll et al. (2016) offer predictive inbound logistics planning. Klumpp (2018) developed a thorough conceptual framework to distinguish logistics human-artificial collaboration systems. This approach sought to improve logistics efficiency and sustainability. The hybrid logistics workflow optimizer (LOW) by Ho et al. (2006) combines Online Analytical Processing and Genetic Algorithm. This hybrid solution improves logistical efficiency and productivity, helping decision-makers manage a changing environment. Whereas (C. K. M. Lee et al., 2011) have examined how AI and RFID might improve logistics workflow systems by acquiring updated information and utilizing relevant knowledge to support demand management.

- The concept of production refers to the process of creating goods or services through the utilization of re-sources:

Six articles relate to production. Two academic papers focus on production forecasting using Artificial Neural Network (ANN) technology. Negash and Yaw (2020) offer an ANN model to estimate oil, gas, and water output in a water-flooded reservoir. For solar still produce prediction, Elsheikh et al. (2021) suggest using a long short-term memory (LSTM) neural network model. An RFID-based intelligent decision support system architecture for remote manufacturing production monitoring and scheduling (Guo et al., 2015) was described. The RFID architecture's adaptability and scalability allow it to integrate with supply chain manufacturing decision-making, production, and logistical processes. Ławrynowicz (2008) suggests integrating AI, expert system, and genetic algorithm for supply chain production planning and scheduling. The proposed method first fixes the production issue, then the scheduling issues. Taylan and Darrab (2012) propose a fuzzy control chart design solution for quality monitoring using artificial intelligence. Waschneck et al. (2018) used the Deep Q Network and user-defined objectives to optimize scheduling and achieve industry 4.0 production management.

- The term "supply chain" refers to the interconnected network of organizations, individuals, activities, information, and resources involved in the production:

Eight supply chain studies were reviewed. Three supply chain management studies address demand forecasting. Amirkolaii et al. (2017) and Mobarakeh et al. (2017) investigated the best forecasting method for high-uncertainty and unpredictable demand, which leads to erroneous projections. The business under consideration may suffer financially from these errors. Amirkolaii et al. (2017) considered an artificial neural network (ANN) strategy more effective, while Mobarakeh et al. (2017) recommended Boot Strapping (BS). In cases with little information and confusing consumer demand, Efendigil et al. (2009) propose using artificial neural networks (ANN) with fuzzy approaches to forecast and handle fuzzy demand. Two academic articles examine supplier selection. A fuzzy Bayesian model by Ferreira and Borenstein (2012) rates and evaluates suppliers for supplier selection.

Instead, Vahdani et al. (2012) suggested a linear neuro-fuzzy model to predict supplier performance. A bio-inspired algorithm by Zhang et al. (2017) designs efficient supply chain networks in competitive oligopoly markets. Baryannis et al. (2019) focus on a data-driven AI system for supply chain risk prediction. This methodology helps supply chain stakeholders make risk-mitigation and prevention decisions. Sinha et al. (2012) suggested a hyper-mutated co-evolutionary immuno-particle swarm optimization approach. This algorithm was created to solve the inventory replenishment problem in the distributed plant, warehouse, and retailer setting.

- Sales and Operations Planning (S&OP) is a strategic business process:

According to Schlegel et al. (2020), the implementation benefits of big data analytics facilitate the advancement of integrated business planning and sales and operations planning (S&OP) dimensions, including meetings and

collaboration, organizational aspects, performance measurement, and information technology (IT), in alignment with the current maturity stage. Sales and Operations Planning (S&OP) is a strategic business process that aims to align.

2. The existing body of literature explores the application of AI/ML technology in addressing various difficulties within supply chain operations.

Table 3 categorizes and shows SCOR model findings by planning, manufacturing, sourcing, delivery, and enabling to answer RQ 2. The results were divided into supply chain issues that AI/ML can solve.

SCOR	Challenges	AI/ML Technologies	Sources
Plan	High volatility, uncertainty, irregular, and fluctuating demand of the products and market. Planning under lead time uncertainties	Artificial Neural Network (ANN)	(Amirkolaii et al., 2017)
		Support Vector Machine (SVM)	(Gecevska, 2017, p. 403)
		Hybrid AI (ARIMAX)	(Feizabadi, 2020)
		Genetic Algorithm (GA)	(Hnaien et al., 2009)
Source	Delay in the supplier selection process, and constraints in supplier relationship management.	ANN	(Choy et al., 2004)
		Hybrid AI	(Lau et al., 2005)
Make	Complexity in monitoring	ANN, Agent-based system	(Monostori, 2003)
Deliver	Service management under uncertain environment	Deep learning	(Ren et al., 2020a)
Enable	Complexities in measuring and evaluating organization performance	Fuzzy logic	(Arshinder et al., 2007)

Table 3: The findings pertaining to RQ 2 are presented in this section

Consumer demand and behavior are driving global supply chain transformations. Meeting client expectations while overcoming operational issues is difficult. The results in Table [number] illustrate that supply chain sectors have benefited from new AI and ML technology. These creative methods have improved risk management, problem-solving, competitiveness, and investment viability.

Five studies evaluated how artificial intelligence addresses various supply and demand planning issues. Gallego-García and García-García (2021) developed a predictive model using artificial neural networks (ANN) to enhance sales and operations planning (S&OP) accuracy and stability, especially in volatile market demand. According to Amirkolaii et al. (2017), artificial neural networks (ANN) may be used to manage demand, supply, and inventory in irregular and uncertain demand fluctuations to improve customer satisfaction. Gecevska (2017) suggests using support vector machines (SVM) to accurately estimate demand to reduce the impact of uncertain swings on supply chain operations and planning.

Feizabadi (2020) proposes a hybrid AI demand forecasting method using ML and neural networks. This strategy addresses financial and coordination limits in supply chain operations and management caused by changing consumer demand. Hnaien et al. (2009) recommend the genetic algorithm for supply planning in two-level assembly systems with lead time uncertainty.

There are two source-related articles. Lau et al. (2005) and Choy et al. (2004) focused on client selection, customer relationship management, and purchase information.

Choy et al. (2004) created an intelligent supplier relationship management system using artificial neural network (ANN) technology to reduce supplier selection delays during new product development with high accuracy. Lau et al. (2005) proposed a hybrid AI knowledge-based system using neural networks and online analytical processing (OLAP) applications. Since the market is unpredictable and supplier selection can take time, this system manages procurement information and selects supply partners. In complex manufacturing, Monostori (2003) stressed the importance of monitoring and controlling different changes and uncertainties in manufacturing process matters. Instead, they recommend Artificial Neural Network (ANN) and Agent-Based systems for complicated industrial problems.

Ren et al. (2020b) developed a deep learning-based logistics service demand management decision-making method for high uncertainty. Arshinder et al. (2007) used fuzzy logic and the analytic hierarchy process (AHP) to measure and assess supply chain partner coordination in an organization. This method evaluates collaboration in contract agreement, communication, information sharing, and IT use.

1. Which measures are employed to evaluate the implementation of artificial intelligence and machine learning in supply chain operations?

Table 4 categorises Research Question 3 findings by domains and metrics techniques. This classification tries to show the metrics and methods used to measure supply chain performance, sales and operations planning (S&OP), and AI/ML.

Fields	Metrics Technologies	Sources
Supply chain performance	AHP, PGP, ANP, DEA	(Bhagwat & Sharma, 2009), (Trivedi & Rajesh, 2013), (Balfaqih et al., 2016), (Drzymalski et al., 2010), (Wong & Wong, 2007)
S&OP	Performance measurement framework	(Hulthén et al., 2016)
AI/ML	RMSE, MAPE	(Wang et al., 2009)

Table 4: The results for Research Question 3

Due to globalization, outsourcing, information technology, and the demand for integration, modern organizations struggle to evaluate output, monitor processes, and make educated decisions. These novel aspects have spurred new perspectives on management functions in business, along with the implementation of appropriate performance measures and metrics to optimise supply chain operations (Balfaqih et al., 2016).

- The topic of interest is the performance of supply chains.

There are six metrics methodologies and a framework for measuring supply chain performance, as well as AI/ML techniques. Bhagwat and Sharma (2009) used the analytical hierarchy process (AHP) and pre-emptive goal programming (PGP) to identify key performance indicators and metrics that can improve supply chain efficiency. Trivedi and Rajesh (2013) recommend using Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) analysis to select KPIs for supply chain performance assessment in business. According to Balfaqih et al. (2016), the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) and Analytic Network Processes (ANP) are qualitative multi-attribute decision-making methods. These methods provide a systematic way to communicate performance measurements. Drzymalski et al. (2010) propose measuring supply chain

efficiency using intra- and inter-organizational parameters. This method combines AHP and ANP elements. As it includes qualitative and quantitative indicators, the data envelopment analysis model (DEA) is useful for assessing organisations with multiple inputs and outputs (Balfaqih et al., 2016). The Wong and Wong (2007) tool uses the DEA model to evaluate internal supply chain efficiency in the face of uncertain environmental changes. It helps discover and fix wasteful processes, enabling improvement decisions.

- Sales and Operations Planning (S&OP)

Hulthén et al. (2016) developed a methodology to evaluate Sales and Operations Planning. Completeness, internal process efficiency, horizontal or vertical integration, internal comparability, and usefulness are criteria. The framework helps organizations undertake efficiency optimization projects with realistic recommendations. It would also help organizations standardize and improve accountability.

- Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML)

AI/ML is widely used in banking, marketing, and healthcare. Performance measurement is needed to assess AI/ML methods' benefits. Wang et al. (2009) developed four quantitative statistical performance metrics. Performance evaluation of AI/ML methods like autoregressive moving-average (ARMA) models, artificial neural network (ANN), adaptive neural-based fuzzy inference system (ANFIS), genetic programming (GP) models, and support vector machine (SVM) method can be done using statistical measures like R, E, RMSE, and MAPE.

3. The following information is presented. The research suggests that there are some characteristics that are crucial for the successful implementation of artificial intelligence and machine learning technologies in supply chain operations?

As shown in Table 5, Research Question 4 (RQ4) findings show the core capabilities needed to improve supply chain operations and integrate AI/ML technology.

Capabilities	Description	Sources
Resilience Capability	Resilience is the capability to respond to unexpected disturbances and disruptions in the supply chain operations	(Yu et al., 2019)
Dynamic and agile capabilities	Helps to develop abilities to achieve strategic advantages in highly changing and dynamic environments	(Rasouli et al., 2015), (Masteikaa, 2015), (Asabe et al., 2020)
Absorptive capability	Enables recognition and utilization of relevant knowledge to improve the collaborative process over time	(Zacharia et al., 2011)
collaborative process competence capability	Enables the process of sharing relevant information, managing conflict, assessing options, jointly making decisions, and combining resources to accomplish objectives collaboratively	(Zacharia et al., 2011)
Management capabilities	Enables to smoothly manage the complexities in all fields of supply chain operations.	(Gunasekaran et al., 2017)
Big data capabilities	effectively leveraging a resource such as big data can lead to significant profit	(Yu et al., 2018)
Data management and analytics capabilities	It helps access accurate information, manage the critical portion of the data, and provide data integration as a single source for applying relevant analytics techniques.	(Hua et al., 2015)
Performance measurement capabilities	Helps to evaluate the overall supply chain operations, decision making, and customer satisfaction	(Thakkar, 2011)

Table 5 The findings for Research Question 4

Capabilities are complex combinations of skills and knowledge that help organisations organize and use their assets (Yu et al., 2018). Rajaguru and Jekanyika (2013) describe supply chain competency as the organization's ability to recognize, use, and integrate internal and external resources and information to support supply chain activities. Nine talents were better for supply chain operations when adopting new innovative technology to optimize performance. Due to changing market conditions and technology, supply chains are becoming more dynamic, making material flow management more complicated and more susceptible to interruptions. In a market with increased unpredictability, organizations can prioritize resilience capabilities to overcome disruptions and survive. Yu et al. (2019) define supply chain resilience capability as a supply chain's ability to predict and prepare for unexpected events, respond quickly to disruptions, and recover from them. Keeping activities running while maintaining supply chain interconnectivity and control achieves this capacity. Dynamic capabilities let supply chain management detect and adapt to environmental changes, according to Rasouli et al. (2015). Researchers studied digital alternatives, agility, and entrepreneurial awareness as dynamic qualities.

Digital alternatives focus on process- and knowledge-oriented information systems and information technology-enabled capabilities. Entrepreneurial awareness is a system's ability to actively explore markets using existing knowledge and proactive experiments to find and respond to possibilities. Agility is the ability to spot innovation opportunities and seize them with the right resources. Customer, collaboration, and operational agility are linked. Masteikaa (2015) defines dynamic capability as the ability to build and modify resources to meet goals in uncertain conditions. Unlike Rasouli et al. (2015), Masteikaa (2015) emphasizes Sensing, Seizing, and Reconfiguring.

Agile skills help optimise sustainability practises, improving environmental and social sustainability performance, according to Asabe et al. (2020). Agile skills can improve knowledge management, leadership, organizational learning, culture, interdisciplinary teams, decentralized decision-making, and customer and stakeholder engagement. Collaboration is crucial to improving organizations' core strengths and strategic capacities in the ever-changing business landscape. Establishing collaborative relationships with suppliers, consumers, and even competitors is increasingly important for organizations' business strategies and competitive edge. Zacharia et al. (2011) defined cooperation as the integration and use of external and internal information and capabilities. The researchers also examined absorptive ability and collaboration process competence, which affect operational and relational results of collaborative endeavors.

Absorptive competence is the ability to recognize and use new ideas, be open to change, and create an environment that encourages innovation. Organisations that can adapt to new ideas are more likely to invest time and resources in external partnerships in the hope of a high return. In a changing global landscape, collaborative methods help organizations identify the knowledge they need from external sources and the skills they need internally. Firms can collaborate on problem-solving instead of learning and solving alone. By doing so, they can use their partners' knowledge to take advantage of complementarities. Collaborative process management helps manage the entire cooperation process, including partner and participant selection, knowledge sharing and synthesis, and process monitoring and adjustment to ensure timely and effective completion.

Effectively managing a dynamic, complicated supply chain is difficult for all parties involved. Supply chain management faces many challenges, including globalization, rising logistics costs, product diversity, shorter product life spans, increased risk, rising labor costs in developing nations, rapid information technology advancement, sustainability concerns, and commodity price volatility. Future supply networks require competent, adaptable personnel to solve these issues. Supply chain management requires specific skills for each task. The study by Gunasekaran et al. (2017) proposed a method for effective supply chain management. Organizations must develop various skills to manage their complicated operations. These include complexity management, information systems management, supply chain knowledge management, relationship management within process capabilities, performance measurement, risk management, and talent management. Data from many sources and structures accumulates quickly in supply chain activities. Big data must be handled efficiently to get a competitive edge in finance,

procedures, and planning. Yu et al. (2018) proposed a framework with four key characteristics for big data management. The four capabilities considered are information exchange, interfirm cooperation, activity integration, and supply chain responsiveness. Big data, with four essential capabilities, can generate significant financial rewards if used strategically. Hua et al. (2015) argue that supply chain success depends on improving big data analysis and interpretation. Analysis methods include predictive analytics, data mining, case-based reasoning, exploratory data analysis, business intelligence, and machine learning. These methods can help companies understand customers' preferences and wants by pulling insights from unstructured data. Organizational performance measurement aids decision-making, process planning, and customer satisfaction. Thakkar (2011) proposed performance measuring capacity to evaluate organizational performance.

Results and discussion

Simple Linear Regression (SLR) research highlights many AI technologies used across supply chain operating phases. Competitive economies' supply chains are changing due to globalization and complexity. Supply chain management increasingly relies on information-intensive processes. AI and machine learning in inventory management, demand and supply forecasting, transportation logistics, procurement, and operations planning are driving this change (Toorajipour et al., 2021). AI-focused supply chain operations and sales and operations planning (S&OP) research has grown, according to the literature. This study examines the relationship between artificial intelligence (AI) and supply chain operational and planning features using relevant keywords, hence the results are confined to supply chain and sales and operations planning (S&OP). My understanding of "dic" is lacking. In Table 2, AI/ML is employed across the supply chain. Demand and sales planning, inventory replenishment, production monitoring, incoming and outbound logistics, supply chain risk management, and integrated business planning are examples. To justify their AI application, these supply chain subfields need a decision-making framework. Artificial intelligence and machine learning improve decision-making by digesting data, identifying trends, forecasting, and anticipating.

Table 2 lists seven AI/ML forecasting experiments. Supply chain AI/ML can forecast accurately. To make educated judgments and maximize business profitability, supply chain operations require excellent forecasting, according to Efendigil et al. (2009). Artificial intelligence and machine learning have unexpectedly risen in forecasting, production planning, inventory management, and logistics. The results reveal that AI and ML can create a completely automated and self-regulating supply chain. AI helps supply chain managers estimate demand and adjust material delivery routes and amounts. After evaluating literature on AI/ML in supply chain operation and S&OP, proposed methodologies and capabilities are scarce. Supplier planning includes Sales and Operations Planning. This study discovered minimal data on AI/ML's impact on Sales and Operations Planning. Big Data maturity helps business forecasting and Sales and Operations Planning (S&OP), according to Schlegel et al. (2020). Collaborations, meetings, organizational structure, success indicators, and IT are mentioned.

Table 3 illustrates how AI/ML solves supply chain and operations planning issues. To predict demand and supply in high-volatility markets, Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) are often used. García and García-García (2021) and Amirkolaii et al. (2017) propose artificial neural networks (ANN) for decision-making and operations planning, especially under uncertain demand and market fluctuations. In 2004, Choy et al. developed an ANN-based intelligent supplier relationship management system. The goal was to speed up supplier selection during new product development. ANN-based forecasting and decision-making are prevalent in production monitoring and transportation services. Cluster analysis-fuzzy learning segmentation is fuzzy models' second most prevalent strategy. This method enhances organizational performance evaluation. In a complex business, evaluating supply chain partners' coordination, contractual arrangements, communication, information exchange, and IT use is tough. According to Arshinder et al. (2007), fuzzy logic solves this problem well. In a turbulent market with variable product demand, SVM, machine learning, and neural networks can make accurate forecasts (Feizabadi, 2020) (Gecevska, 2017). Hnaien et al. (2009)

suggested utilizing a genetic algorithm (GA) for supply planning in two-level assembly systems with lead time uncertainty, along with ANN, SVM, ML, and fuzzy logic. Monostori (2003) advocates monitoring and managing manufacturing process changes and uncertainties with an agent-based system. Artificial intelligence and machine learning have improved supply chains. Data extraction from a specific system, data formats needed for analysis, database integration with AI/ML software, and data governance in inter-organizational data sharing lack statistical significance.

Table 4 reveals strategies, tools, and approaches for discovering the most essential supply chain performance KPIs. These solutions enable KPI selection and structured communication for various performance measurements. They assess corporate processes and optimize the supply chain. Bhagwat and Sharma (2009) and Trivedi and Rajesh (2013) revealed intriguing results. To choose supply chain KPIs and performance metrics, the authors recommend AHP and ANP models. Data envelopment analysis (DEA) by Wong and Wong (2007) identifies unnecessary processes and supports improvement decisions. Selling and Operations Planning performance evaluation is organized by Hulthén et al. (2016). Comprehensiveness, internal process performance, horizontal and vertical integration, internal comparability, and utility are measures used in this paradigm. Use these criteria to make specific recommendations for firms aiming to improve S&OP processes by establishing and implementing performance metrics. Write "The user's text pertains to the concepts of effectiveness and efficiency." Organizations should standardize measurements and boost accountability. AI and machine learning systems' operational effectiveness was tested using four quantitative standard statistical performance evaluation measures. R, E, RMSE, and MAPE have been used to evaluate autoregressive moving-average (ARMA), artificial neural network (ANN), adaptive neural-based fuzzy inference system (ANFIS), genetic programming (GP), and support vector machine (SVM) methodologies. Results show evolving supply chain operations, AI/ML, and sales and operations planning evaluation methods. Supply chain operations and S&OP ignore AI and machine learning metrics.

Table 5 indicates that supply chain effectiveness depends on core competences, especially when introducing new technology. Despite unexpected environmental, customer, and managerial changes, the supply chain must be handled well. Organizations need supply chain expertise. In turbulent environments, dynamic and agile talent is vital for strategic advantage. Rasouli et al. (2015) said any organization needs dynamic ability to react to fast-changing surroundings. Yu et al. (2019) found that resilience helped the organization handle supply chain interruptions. Supply chain management must be efficient because it is data-driven and coupled with other company processes. Complex supply chains demand collaboration and management (Zacharia et al., 2011) (Gunasekaran, 2017). The results surprised since they tested dynamic, resilience, managerial, data management, analytical, and performance assessment capacities. Data management and analytical capabilities enable a company to gather accurate data, manage vital data, and integrate data as a platform for applicable analytics approaches, according to Hua et al. (2015). To generate insights and improve decision-making, managing massive amounts of data from numerous systems and sources requires the above competencies. Monitor supply chain performance to make efficient decisions. Businesses need performance evaluation to measure their entire performance (Thakkar, 2011). Strategy for adopting new technology and adjusting to supply chain disruptions requires defined skills.

Conclusions

Finally, service attributes, quality attributes, and social attributes are the top areas where manufacturers should focus to optimize their products and services because they can have a negative impact on consumer satisfaction. This research may have certain limitations due to the diversity of the customer groups. The results based on LDA topic modeling, for example, may be impacted by false reviews or intentionally negative reviews created by customer groups due to brand loyalty. To increase the effectiveness of review data for business service development and product optimization, it can be considered including customer demographic factors as a component into the research and classification of customer group review behavior characteristics

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Supply Chain Management adaptive equalization is a promising field of research.

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